

INDIAN CONFRONTATION TO ECOMMERCE

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ABSTRACT

The eCommerce sector has seen unprecedented growth in 2014. The growth was driven by rapid technology adoption led by the increasing use of devices such as smart phones and tablets, and access to the internet through broadband, 3G, etc, which led to an increased online consumer base. Furthermore, favoured demographics and a growing internet user base helped aid this growth. In terms of highlights, the growth shown by home grown players such as Flipkart and Snapdeal and the huge investor interest around these companies displayed the immense potential of the market. With the entry of eCommerce behemoths such as Amazon and Alibaba, the competition is expected to further intensify. Both these international players come with deep pockets and the patience to drive the Indian eCommerce market. Also, their strong domain knowledge and best practices from their international experience give them an additional edge. Additionally, these companies have been part of markets where they have seen the eCommerce market evolve and are aware of the challenges and strategies to address issues thereof.

Keywords: Demonetisation, Internet Banking, Retailing, Marketing

1. INTRODUCTION

Technology plays a vital role in improving the quality of services provided by the business units. One of the technologies which really brought information revolution in the society is Internet Technology and is rightly regarded as the third wave of revolution after agricultural and industrial revolution. The cutting edge for business today is e-Commerce. The effects of e-commerce are already appearing in all areas of business, from customer service to new product design. It facilitates new types of information based business processes for reaching and interacting with customers like online advertising and marketing, online order taking and online customer service etc. It can also reduce cost in managing orders and interacting with a wide range of suppliers and trading partners, areas that typically add significant overheads to the cost of products and services. Businesses are increasingly using the Internet for commercial activities. The ubiquitous nature of the Internet and its wide global access has made it an extremely effective mode of communication between businesses and customers.

Electronic commerce, commonly known as eCommerce, consists of the buying and selling of products or services over electronic system such as internet and other computer network. Intent is the technology for e-commerce as it

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offers easier ways to access companies and individuals at very low cost order to carry out day-to-day business transactions.

Search engine marketing (SEM) is a form of web advertising that companies use to promote their products and services on search engine results pages (SERPs). SEM is focused on the effective use of search engine advertisements (a.k.a., sponsored results, sponsored links) that appear on the SERP. SEM which allows firms to target consumers by placing ads on search engines has proven to be an effective audience acquisition strategy. Unlike traditional online advertising, advertisers pay only when users actually click on an ad when successfully implemented, SEM can generate steady traffic levels and tremendous return on investment (ROI).

The differences between the traditional retail model and the concept of selling goods online

Figure 1. Different Models

As can be clearly seen, the e-tail model does not have to invest in brick-and-mortar stores, but have to arrange for delivery logistics instead. There seems to be lesser intervention between the product and its delivery to the customer in comparison to traditional retail where the product has to pass through several middlemen who do the sorting and storage. Quite obviously, this means that e-tail is much more flexible in terms of gaining a much larger customer base.

1. 1 Types of E-Commerce

Waghmare G.T. has defined the following types of e-commerce:

- (i) B2B E-Commerce: Companies doing business with each other such as manufacturers selling to distributors and wholesalers selling to retailers. Pricing is based on quantity of order and is often negotiable.
- (ii) B2C E-Commerce: Businesses selling to the general public typically through catalogues utilizing shopping cart software. By dollar volume, B2B takes the prize, however B2C is really what the average Joe has in mind with regards to ecommerce as a whole. For example indiatimes.com.
- (iii) C2C E-Commerce: There are many sites offering free classifieds, auctions, and forums where individuals can buy and sell thanks to online payment systems like PayPal where people can send and receive money online with ease. eBay's auction service is a great example of where customer-to customer transactions take place every day.
- (iv) Others: G2G (Government-to-Government), G2E (Government-to-Employee), G2B (Government-to-Business), B2G (Business-to-Government).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature on web theory is scant because it is a relatively a new area and the technologists at the forefront of Web design are typically not sufficiently academically inclined to formulate the relevant theories (Day, 1997). While previous research has examined Internet usage (Teo, Lim, & Lai, 1999), commercial websites (Gonzalez and Palacios, 2004), website design (Kim, Shaw, & Schneider, 2003), website effectiveness from the consumers' perspective (Bell & Tang, 1998), pricing paid placements on search engine (Sen et. al., 2008), and bidding (Bernard and Simone, 2011). This form of online advertising emerged in 1998 [Fain and Pedersen 2006], rapidly has become the central business model of the major search engines [Jansen and Mullen 2008], and is one of the most rapidly growing segments of the online marketing area [SEMPO Research 2009] Search engine has become a necessity for people to surf the web [Hsien-Tsung Chang, 2011]. It is a simple user interface is designed. Any user simply fills in several fields and the system makes the decision about what to find, where to search and how to look at. The threshold of search is lowered. SEM is an internet marketing model aiming at promoting the ranking of websites in the search engine's search results page which can make a web site introduce into more web users and website traffic [iProspect 2008]. Li-Hsing HO et. al., (2011) explained about exploration of SEO technology applied in internet marketing, Kesharwani and Tiwari (2011) studied the importance of website quality towards the success or failure of any e-vendor. Khan and Mahapatra (2009) studied that the quality of internet banking (i-banking) services in India from customer's perspective. Malhotra and Singh (2007) carried out a research to find the i-banking adoption by the banks in India. Thus, it is high time that India should act fast and decisively in order to use the growing electronic trade to our advantage

NEED FOR DIFFERENT MANAGEMENT OF PHYSICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

The business model of the conventional retailers and e-commerce providers differ significantly. The conventional infrastructure model relies on increasing depth and breadth of coverage through several inventory nodes, warehouses and stocking points connected by based on various other factors ranging from production cycles, nature and variety of the SKUs to even local taxation laws. The conventional order point occurs at retail stores and static customer fronts located at the end of the chain, and inventory requirements are predicted empirically based on several months or years of past data. In fact, competing sales channels may also duplicate infrastructure, an indication of the typical subordination of the logistics function within the overall sales and distribution process.

3. CHALLENGES FOR INDIAN E-COMMERCE SITES IN DYNAMIC MARKET

After burning billions in venture capital, Indian e-commerce companies are now realising that there's no such thing as unlimited funding, impressive losses are a thing of the past and they need real profits. Investors who were hitherto encouraging entrepreneurs to acquire customers at any cost and show meaningless GMV (gross merchandise value) have all flipped in a snap and are now pushing the same entrepreneurs to urgently become profitable and the entrepreneurs are like deer in the headlights. This situation is not surprising at all. With so much capital and resources at their command, Indian e-commerce firms should have focused on building delightful customer experiences using the simple CAPS framework — Convenience, Availability, Pricing and Selection. Simply put, e-commerce sites must make available to their shoppers a wide selection of great merchandise at attractive prices delivered reliably and conveniently. And the harsh truth is they have miserably failed on this account despite promising so much. Today they are facing a relentless onslaught from Amazon — the gold standard in online shopping globally who is rapidly luring away all people through excellence in customer experience — and probably ruing the fact that they could have done things differently.

As a shopper, can you think of a single reason why you would shop at a Flipkart or Snapdeal over Amazon. Higher quality merchandise? Unique stuff? Better laid out website? Faster app? Lower prices? More reliable deliveries? Amazon's increasing market share in India will provide the answers.

In reality, Indian e-commerce firms have been distracted from the core principles of online shopping. Have you ever wondered why electronic commerce is popularly referred to as e-commerce and not electronic-c? This is because despite all the technology hype surrounding electronic commerce, the business was, is and will always remain about the commerce. When you fly from Mumbai to Delhi, do you choose an airline that has convenient timings, low prices and a reputation for good service? Or do you evaluate carefully between Boeing and Airbus aircraft powered by Rolls-Royce or Pratt & Whitney engines? Will you shop regularly at a site that offers great service experiences or at a competing app which employs more computer programmers at high salaries? There is an apocryphal story about a bright student, furiously writing his examinations, getting distracted by an irritating mosquito. He immediately squashes the mosquito resulting in bloody smears on the answer paper.

A neighbouring student, blindly copying from this student gets flustered by this sudden action and immediately starts searching for another mosquito to squash on his answer paper as well. Indian e-commerce firms have taken a similar

approach in trying to do whatever Amazon is doing. Instead of building business moats around their ventures, they have gone down the anachronistic path of building a technology start-up because Amazon is a tech company by hiring a bloated staff of highly overpaid engineers, including from Silicon Valley, to aid them in their goal of building a very high tech consumer internet firm. This narrative also found enthusiastic favour with global investors who were happy to write big cheques supporting “consumer technology” firms because it was part of their portfolio strategy instead of funding entrepreneurs building sustainable ventures. So, what’s the problem? Haven’t the likes of Amazon and Ebay built successful e-commerce businesses by being a consumer tech firm? Yes, they have. The problem is the timing. When Amazon and Ebay pioneered global e-commerce in the mid-1990s, they had no choice but to build their own technology platforms by hiring teams of engineers and they continued with this strategy as they expanded. Two decades later, thanks to the popularity of low cost (almost 1/1000th), fully featured, high quality SaaS (software as a service) platforms, hiring large teams of expensive engineers to build e-commerce engines is passes. Worse, the mindset becomes a challenge. You think in a certain way when you start a technology firm with unlimited funding and then suddenly, against your wishes, you are dragged kicking and screaming to make a transition to a frugal merchandise and operations focused retail firm. This is a challenge that can destroy most organisations, which is what we are currently seeing all around us.

4. IMPLEMENTATION OF GST EXPECTED TO ELIMINATE MOST TAX ISSUES

Online retailers are looking forward to the implementation of Goods and Services Tax (GST), since it would help iron out most of the tax issues. CST and VAT will be subsumed in the GST; this would ensure:

- Uniform rate of GST on a product across all of the states
- GST to be creditable against IGST, which will be levied on inter-state transfer of goods

To explain how online retailers and consumers would benefit from the creditability aspect of GST, consider the following cases: A manufacturer can sell goods to an online retailer, either in its own state or in another one, which can then sell these goods to end consumers located in the same state or otherwise. In the diagrams below, letters A, B and C denote states.

Figure. 2. Barriers to paying online

While the e-commerce sector is popular amongst consumers there are of course barriers that prevent some people from shopping online. Fraud and control are the main concerns preventing consumers from paying online. For half of European online shoppers, concern about fraud is the primary barrier to online payments. The trend is consistent across countries, although concern about fraud is highest in Greece, with 71% of people stating that it is an issue, with 64% of Spaniards also feeling fraud is a problem. The lowest level of concern about fraud is in Denmark, with less than half of people surveyed (46%) stating that it is a barrier. What is positive for the potential growth of e-commerce is that barriers such as 'not knowing how it works' (12 %) and 'acceptance of the payment' (14%) are at the lower end of the scale. This suggests consumers are indeed willing and able to shop and pay online and so long as issues around security and trust are addressed consumers will engage.

4.CONCLUSION

Like many other sectors, the on-going cash crunch has impacted online shopping. To tackle growing cancellations, leading e-commerce companies had to limit or suspend payments through cash-on-delivery, the most preferred choice of payment, Mint reported on 10 November. Typically, about 70% of the overall e-commerce orders are paid for in cash, according to research and advisory firm Red seer Management. This has changed drastically after demonetisation, and will impact the e-commerce business in India where a large portion of the population is still unbanked, said eMarketer. The researcher also trimmed its 2020 forecast to \$47.45 billion from \$79.41 billion it estimated in August. I found various types of opportunities for retailers, wholesalers/distributors, producers and also for people. Retailers meet electronic orders and should be in touch with the consumers all the time. Wholesalers can take advantage of E-Commerce who are capable of establishing contractors with reputed producers and linking their business with the on- line. Producers can also linking themselves with on-line, by giving better information about their products to the other links in the business chain and by a having a brand identity. As more people are getting linked with E-commerce, the demand for centre providing internet facility or cyber cafe is also increasing. Hence, the people who wish to take advantage of it can establish cyber and have their benefits. People could found various opportunities of employment. On the behalf of above said reports and experts view showed that the future of e-commerce in India would be bright in the upcoming years if all essential factors would be implemented.

Over the last two decades, rising internet and mobile phone penetration has changed the way we communicate and do business. E-commerce is relatively a novel concept. It is, at present, heavily leaning on the internet and mobile phone revolution to fundamentally alter the way businesses reach their customers.

ABBREVIATIONS

1. Ecommerce - Electronic Commerce
2. SEM - Search engine marketing
3. SERP- Search engine results pages
4. ROI - Return on investment
5. G2G - Government-to-Government
6. G2E - Government-to-Employee
7. G2B - Government-to-Business
8. B2G - Business-to-Government

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